

Synthetic and Antimicrobial Studies of some Bivalent Metal Chelates of Heterocyclic Anils

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A broad spectrum of biological activity is reported to be associated with a number of heterocyclic compounds¹. It has also been established that biological activity of a ligand is altered many folds on its coordination with suitable metal ions².

We report here the synthesis of three heterocyclic anils derived from 2-acetylthiophene, anthra-

nilic acid and 2-aminothiophenol and their bis-complexes with Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and Zn^{II}. Antimicrobial activity of the ligands and their complexes have been evaluated against gram positive (*Staphylococcus aureus*), gram negative (*Escherichia coli*) bacteria and *Aspergillus niger* and *Candida albicans* fungi.

Results and Discussion

All the solid complexes are coloured and stable at room temperature. They are insoluble in organic solvents except DMF, DMSO and propylene glycol. M.ps. were determined by open capillary method and are uncorrected. Low molar conductance values ($5.60-8.85 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) indicate their non-electrolytic nature. Analytical data (Table 1) suggest 1 : 2 (M : L) stoichiometry.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF LIGANDS AND COMPLEXES

Compd. (Colour)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			
	C	H	N	M
ATATP (HL) (Dark black)	70.78 (71.86)	5.30 (5.48)	7.40 (7.47)	—
CuL ₂ (Black)	62.44 (62.13)	4.50 (4.32)	5.87 (6.04)	14.12 (13.71)
NiL ₂ (Black)	61.68 (62.79)	4.60 (4.36)	5.84 (6.10)	12.98 (12.79)
CoL ₂ ·2H ₂ O (Light pink)	58.00 (58.19)	4.47 (4.84)	5.82 (5.65)	11.28 (11.91)
ZnL ₂ ·2H ₂ O (Brown)	57.00 (57.44)	4.60 (4.78)	5.37 (5.58)	13.20 (13.04)
ATAA (HL) (Dark brown)	63.00 (63.67)	4.33 (4.49)	5.45 (5.71)	—
CuL ₂ (Dark blue)	56.00 (56.65)	3.27 (3.63)	5.00 (5.07)	12.00 (11.52)
NiL ₂ (Green)	56.90 (57.07)	3.48 (3.65)	5.43 (5.12)	10.80 (10.73)
CoL ₂ ·2H ₂ O (Pink)	53.27 (53.52)	4.00 (4.11)	4.70 (4.80)	9.98 (10.11)
ZnL ₂ ·2H ₂ O (White)	53.00 (52.94)	4.00 (4.07)	4.42 (4.75)	11.35 (11.09)
AFAA (HL) (Light brown)	68.00 (68.12)	4.47 (4.80)	6.43 (6.11)	—
CuL ₂ (Light green)	59.98 (60.05)	3.80 (3.85)	5.28 (5.39)	12.42 (12.23)
NiL ₂ (Dark green)	60.40 (60.61)	3.68 (3.88)	5.28 (5.44)	11.30 (11.40)
CoL ₂ ·2H ₂ O (Pink)	56.40 (56.63)	4.20 (4.35)	5.22 (5.08)	10.84 (10.69)
ZnL ₂ ·2H ₂ O (White)	55.80 (55.97)	4.20 (4.31)	5.14 (5.02)	11.96 (11.73)

In the ir spectra of ligands ATAA and AFAA, a sharp band at 2875 cm^{-1} due to ν_{OH} of carboxylic group is observed which disappears in the spectra of the corresponding complexes indicating thereby the coordination of the ligand to central metal ion as a consequence of deprotonation of COOH group. ν_{as} and ν_{s} vibrations of the COO⁻ ion appear at 1535 and 1325 cm^{-1} respectively. $\Delta\nu_{(\text{as-s})}$ value (210 cm^{-1}) further indicates unidentate nature of the carboxylate group³. A weak band at 2850 cm^{-1} (SH) in the spectra of ATATP, disappears in the spectra of the respective metal complexes, suggesting thereby deprotonation of thiol group during coordination. Ir spectra of all the ligands show a sharp band around 1620 cm^{-1} (C=N) which is shifted to lower frequency region by $20-25 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, suggesting participation of azomethine N in complexation.

In case of the Co^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes, the presence of coordinated water molecules is shown by the appearance of a sharp peak at 3450 cm^{-1}

followed by a sharp band at 810 cm^{-1} . TG analysis also confirms the presence of two moles of coordinated water in the Co^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes, as the mass-loss was found to be equivalent to two moles of water. Some new bands found in the far-ir spectra of the complexes around $530-540$, $440-450 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $340-325 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, support the formation of M-O, M-N and M-S bonds respectively⁴, which further confirm that the ligands are mono-basic bidentate (NS/NO) in nature.

¹H nmr spectra of the ligands displays a complex multiplet at $\delta 7.1-7.5$ (aromatic ring protons), a sharp singlet at δ (methyl protons), a sharp singlet at 2.9 (SH) and another singlet at 11.02 (CO₂H). The latter two peaks are absent in the nmr spectra of the respective complexes, inferring thereby deprotonation of thiol and carboxylic group during complexation.

The electronic spectra of the Cu^{II} complexes display four bands at $37000-37150$, $24850-24925$, $14950-14985$ and $17350-17370 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The first two bands are CT bands and the remaining two may be assigned to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ and $\rightarrow {}^2E_g$ transitions respectively, which are in conformity with the square-planar geometry (μ_{eff} values 1.71 (± 0.2) B.M.). Electronic spectra of the Ni^{II} complexes show three bands at 38080 (CT band), 15320 and 17375 cm^{-1} along with a shoulder at 30000 cm^{-1} . The shoulder is of ligand field origin and probably arises from the transition ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1E_g$. The remaining two bands may be assigned to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ and $\rightarrow {}^2E_g$ transitions respectively, under square-planar environment around the metal ion.

The μ_{eff} values of $4.54 (\pm 0.15)$ B.M. and three bands in the electronic spectra of Co^{II} complexes at 8970 , 18600 and 21225 cm^{-1} corresponding to the ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$, $\rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transitions indicate an octahedral geometry for the complexes. As expected all the Zn^{II} complexes are diamagnetic in nature and on the basis of analytical and spectral data an octahedral geometry is proposed for them.

The esr spectra of the Cu^{II} complexes show a sharp band corresponding to the value of $g=2.06$ which is in agreement with the magnetic susceptibility value for Cu^{II} ion, the value required for one unpaired electron⁵.

The biological activity data (Table 2) show that antimicrobial activity of ligand enhances several folds on complexation. This increase in the antimicrobial activity is probably either due to faster diffusion of metal complexes as a whole through the cell membrane or due to the combined activity effect of the metal and ligand⁶.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade.

The ligands, 2-acetylthiophene-2'-aminothiophenol (ATATP), 2-acetylthiophene-anthranilic acid

TABLE 2—ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY (MIC, VALUES, $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)* OF COMPOUNDS

Compd.	S.a	E.c	A.n	C.a
ATATP(HL)	50	25	50	50
CuL ₂	12.5	12.5	6.25	6.25
NiL ₂	6.25	6.25	12.5	12.5
CoL ₂ .2H ₂ O	12.5	12.5	6.25	6.25
ZnL ₂ .2H ₂ O	6.25	6.25	12.5	12.5
ATAA(HL)	100	100	75	75
CuL ₂	12.5	12.5	6.25	6.25
NiL ₂	6.25	6.25	12.5	12.5
CoL ₂ .2H ₂ O	6.25	6.25	12.5	12.5
ZnL ₂ .2H ₂ O	6.25	6.25	6.25	6.25
AFAA(HL)	100	100	100	100
CuL ₂	25	25	12.5	12.5
NiL ₂	12.5	12.5	25	25
CoL ₂ .2H ₂ O	12.5	12.5	25	12.5
ZnL ₂ .2H ₂ O	12.5	12.5	6.25	6.25

*S.a \equiv *S. aureus*, E.c \equiv *E. coli*, A.n \equiv *A. niger*, C.a \equiv *C. albicans*.

(ATAA) and 2-acetyl-furan-anthranilic acid (AFAA) were synthesised by refluxing equimolecular ethanolic solutions of heterocyclic carbonyl compounds and the corresponding amines for ~24 h. On cooling in refrigerator, coloured crystals were separated out which were washed with cold ethanol and dried under reduced pressure over anhydrous CaCl₂.

All the metal complexes were synthesised by adding ethanolic solutions of the metal(II) acetates to an ethanolic solution of the ligand and the reaction mixture was refluxed for ~2 h. The coloured complexes were washed with ethanol followed

by ether and dried under reduced pressure over anhydrous CaCl₂.

All the ligands and their metal complexes were screened in vitro for their antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* (incubation period at 37° for 24 h) and antifungal activity against *A. niger* and *C. albicans* (incubation period at 28° for 96 h). Serial dilution method⁷ was employed to evaluate MIC (minimum inhibitory concentration) values (Table 2).

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